

MEDIA TEXT IN MEDIA LINGUISTICS

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Abstract: The article discusses the concept of media text, areas of their study, aspects of media linguistics and the study of media language. The methodological apparatus, internal structure and main sections of media linguistics are considered.

Keywords: media linguistics, media text, verbal language, phonological, discourse analysis, cognitive, semantic.

Аннотация: Мақоллада медиатекст тushunchasi, ularni o'rganish yo'nalishlari, medialingvistikaning aspektlari va media tilini o'rganish masalalari muhokama qilinadi. Media lingvistikasining uslubiy apparati, ichki tuzilishi va asosiy bo'limlari ko'rib chiqiladi.

Калит so'zlar: media lingvistikasi, media matn, verbal muloqot, fonologik, nutq tahlili, kognitiv, semantik.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются понятие медиатекста, направления их изучения, аспекты медиалингвистики и изучения медиа языка. Рассмотрены методический аппарат, внутренняя структура и основные разделы медиалингвистики.

Ключевые слова: медиалингвистика, медиатекст, вербальный язык, фонологический, дискурсивный анализ, когнитивный.

In world practice, the creation of a solid theory of mass media and speech-thinking activity is an urgent task facing the science of journalism. In the study of mass media, certain methods and analytical processes play an important role (historical, typological, descriptive, social, socio-psychological, discursive, semantic, linguistic, stylistic, structural analyses, content analysis, etc). In this sense, it is extremely important to determine the stylistic state of the language of the media, as well as ways to describe media texts and the influence of sociocultural factors on media speech and the study of linguo-media technologies of influence.

Today in journalism there is a great need for research on the specifics of media texts, namely language, stylistic and genre features, components, tasks of creating and editing media texts. Changes in human consciousness and thinking, social and political events in society directly affect the essence and form of media texts. Therefore, the language and style of the media of each new period reflect the changes of that period and require a separate study.

According to Professor G. Bakieva and Professor D. Teshabaeva, “A separate concept of media text can be considered as the main theoretical component of media linguistics. The essence of this concept is that when the definition is that the text, which is considered basic for traditional linguistics, is “a semantically related sequence of sign units. Its main characteristic is coherence and integrity” [1, 507] is transferred to the field of mass media, it significantly expands its boundaries. In this, the concept of media text goes beyond the sign system at the verbal level and approaches the semiotic interpretation of the concept of text, assuming the unity of not only verbal, but also any signs [2, 71].

Media texts are considered from the standpoint of different schools and trends: sociolinguistics, functional stylistics, discourse theory, content analysis, cognitive linguistics and rhetorical criticism. The ways of creating and distributing media texts depend on their linguistic volume, functional-genre classification, phonological, syntagmatic and stylistic features, interpretation features, cultural-specific features, ideological modelling, and pragmalinguistic value. The methodological basis of the new direction is described as follows: “The methodological apparatus of media linguistics combines the achievements of all areas that study media texts. These include discursive analysis, functional stylistics and linguoculturology” [3, 28].

Undoubtedly, in the field of media linguistics, the group of methods of linguistic analysis plays an important role. “Methods of linguistic analysis are a group of traditional methods of semantic, stylistic, morphological, syntactic analysis of media texts in linguistics. The study of media texts in this way has a long and fruitful tradition [4, 37]. Particularly important is the method of sequential text analysis, which makes it possible to determine the rules for constructing a media text at the syntagmatic and stylistic levels. Analysis at the syntagmatic level shows the presence of a stable paradigm of involvement, characteristic of a particular type of text. For example, the syntagmatic form of news (information-oriented texts) relies mainly on verbal expressions. The method of stylistic analysis is also of great importance. Its purpose is to identify various stylistic means and determine their role in realizing the overall communicative perspective of a media text. It was determined that when conducting a study, it is appropriate to use the linguistic features of media texts, methods analysis, allowing to determine the structure of media texts, analysis of linguistic, stylistic and genre features of media texts. In addition, when studying media texts, the method of

content analysis or the sociological method, the method of discursive analysis, the cognitive method, "reconstruction" ("restructuring"), linguoculturological methods of analysis were used.

Media texts are also classified by type and form: according to the corresponding direction of the media in which they are created, structured and used; by methods of perception; by subjects and areas of activity; by style; by discourse. Undoubtedly, such a classification is mandatory, which makes it possible to divide into main categories.

The main categories of media text are classified as follows:

- media;
- the public (in the sphere of creation and consumption of media products);
- integrativity;
- polycode;
- openness.

According to the theory of M.M. Bakhtin, any "truth in the learning process is accepted as evaluated and regulated from a moral, vital, social and political point of view, this process must have its own position in relation to the reality being studied" [5, 24].

“According to the dominant theme, media texts can be in the form of a stable system of regularly reproduced topics in the media - “buzz-topics” or media topics: politics, business, sports, culture, weather, international and regional news, etc” [8, 43].

Among the most effective and common methods for studying media text are the following:

1. A whole group of methods of linguistic analysis, allowing to determine the main features and characteristics of the text at different levels of language: lexical, syntagmatic (compatibility), stylistic (using tropes, comparisons, metaphors and other stylistic means), sociolinguistic.
2. Content analysis or a method of content analysis based on statistical calculation of specially selected text units.
3. The method of discourse analysis, based on a discursive concept and allowing to determine the ratio of the linguistic and extra-linguistic sides of the text.
4. The method of critical linguistics (or rhetorical criticism), revealing the hidden political and ideological component of the media text.

5. The method of cognitive analysis, based on the study of conceptual aspects of popular texts and aimed at determining the relationship between reality and its media representations.

6. And, finally, the method of linguoculturological (linguoculturological) analysis, based on the identification of culturally significant components of the text, such as reality, assimilated, foreign words, equivalent lexical units, etc. about the features.

Obviously, the group of methods of linguistic analysis is important in the field of media linguistics. “Mass communication is a process (type) of dissemination of information of social-ideological, spiritual and educational significance among a large socially classified, geographically dispersed audience in a form that is evaluated, interpreted and influenced in a mass, accessible style with the help of technical means, and, along with this, is a product of this process. This process consists of the stages of psycholinguistic translation of information into a linguistic expression (speech, text) and its reception, comprehension and awareness. The first stage concerns the activity of the communicator (editorial team), and the second stage concerns the attitude of the addressee (reader, listener or viewer) [7, 49].

Speech impact in the media is based on experimentally tested linguistic, sociolinguistic and psycholinguistic methods. This language apparatus and mass media have their own laws of use. The effectiveness of communication is related to the level of impact on the listener or reader through the appropriate choice and use of language tools. Adequate understanding of speech in accordance with the target setting of the listener and trust in him ensures the effectiveness of communication [7, 132].

A. Abdusaidov writes about increasing the effectiveness of the media text: “In recent years, elements of artistic language have been increasingly used to express expressiveness in the language of the press. This can be seen in the use of pictorial means, proverbs and expressions, and in the extensive use of dialogue in essays, films and articles. Such a situation undoubtedly enriches the newspaper with living materials, attracts the attention of the newspaper reader, helps to quickly understand the material, and increases expressiveness [8, 83].

The effectiveness of communication is related to the degree of impact on the listener or reader through the appropriate choice and use of language tools. For the author, it is important that he makes the right genre and stylistic choice in a realistic

and expressive display of the events of our daily life. The perfection of the printed text depends not only on the skill of the journalist, but also on the skill of the editorial staff, especially the editor. The editor not only corrects the mistakes and shortcomings made by the author, but is also responsible for ensuring that the work meets the requirements and expressiveness. In the expressiveness of media texts, the role of extralinguistic paragraphemic means (highlighting fonts (letters) in black, italics, different colors, sizes; punctuation marks, on which page and where the text is placed) is significant. The above cases contribute to the improvement and expressiveness of the media text.

Media text is the main object of study of media linguistics. The most effective and widespread methods of studying a media text are: linguistic analysis, content analysis, discursive analysis, critical analysis, cognitive analysis and linguoculturological analysis. Through these methods of analysis, it is necessary to adapt modern media texts to the current model of the national language.

Such parameters of media texts as mobility and freedom, globalization, speed, flexibility, interactivity, visibility, etc. it is necessary to scientifically investigate in accordance with the role of mass media in human life and ways to attract people.

The issue of genre is important in mass media. In connection with updates in media genres, changes in the boundaries between genres, the phenomena of interaction between genres of mass communication, normalized correspondence must be approached from the standpoint of journalistic skill.

The media text should embody the features of accuracy, simplicity and conciseness, as well as effectiveness, timeliness, efficiency, novelty, relevance, in general, of all aspects important for society.

The main rule in creating a text is the formation of a journalist's own style. At the same time, there are certain principles of layout and ordering of the text. The author, first of all, based on the needs of the reader (recipient) of the text, chooses the basis and amount of information, the way it is expressed, and also takes into account the type of publication. Accordingly, he must turn to the principles of constructing oral speech, written speech, or their mixed use.

So, a media text is a holistic speech phenomenon, structured and ordered on the basis of semantically and syntactically consistent connections as a natural set of mental and linguistic behavior in accordance with the sphere of communication, type, situation of communication and the author's goal of a certain communicative activity.

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